

An Actual Usage of E-Wallet in Nainital City

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Abstract

A society is divided, in everything that lives in it and its usage affects society itself. Man is such a social animal that is a part of this society. The development or decline of the society all depends on the behavior of the human being. The human brain develops from the interaction or damage of everything, due to which humans use their decision-making ability. Whenever something new has to be done, a person hesitates a little before using it or mostly tries to run away from that thing. But it is a human being who tries to learn something; he goes and soon makes it his lifestyle. Whenever the matter is related to the transaction of human's money, then the person takes that decision by thinking of it carefully. In today's time when the payment system has become completely modern, in such a situation whether a person adopts it or not is his own decision as every modern technology has its own pros & cons.

Key words: E-wallet; Cashless; Technology; Digitization.

Introduction

India is a developing country with a mixed economy. India's steps towards globalization can now be seen in the policies, one of them is Digital India.

Digital India is one such effort which is giving a new identity to India. The transaction of money has seen many ups and downs. Before the advent of money, there was a barter system, next came fiat money and fiduciary money, followed by currency notes, plastic cards, internet banking. Now India has taken a big step towards a modern era, where money has become very secure to a great extent.

Present Scenario as a mode of payment E-Wallet has introduced which has made transactions very easy. Earlier, the difficulty that the customer used to follow the banking system has now gone away.

An e-Wallet is a kind of prepaid account where a user may deposit funds for upcoming online purchases. A password is required to access an e-wallet. One may pay for groceries, internet purchases, and airline tickets with an e-wallet.

Software and data make up the two primary parts of an e-wallet. The software component safeguards and encrypts data while storing personal information. The information component consists of a database with information supplied by users, such as their name, shipping address, preferred method of payment, required payment amount, credit or debit card information, etc.

Objectives

- To identify the role played by e-wallet in promoting cashless transaction in Nainital city.
- To identify socio-demographic factors responsible for e-wallet cashless transaction of Nainital city

Research Methodology

Research Design - Descriptive research design is employed in the study. It describes the numerous traits of the population from which the sample was drawn.

Data Source - In this study, both primary and secondary data are used to try to solve the problems outlined in the objectives.

To obtain the respondents' individual opinions, a questionnaire was sent online and distributed by WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, Gmail, etc. Secondary information has been gathered from a variety of publications and websites.

Sampling Design - The population being surveyed is limited to the NAINITAL CITY over the age of 15 and above.

Sampling size - 161

Sampling Techniques- Non - Probability Convenience sampling

The analysis has been done through MS EXCEL and SPSS 26 by the use of Chi Square Test Etc.

Hypothesis

H₀₁ - There is no impact of Gender of respondents on e-wallet.

Ha₁- There is an impact of Gender of respondents on e-wallet.

H₀₂ - There is no impact of Age of respondents on the e-wallet.

Ha₂ - There is an impact of Age of respondents on the e-wallet.

H₀₃ - There is no impact of Profession of respondents on the e-wallet.

Ha₃ - There is an impact of Profession of respondents on the e-wallet.

Results & Discussion

1. Descriptive Statistics:

I took response of 161 respondent of Nainital city for research. As I wanted to know the actual usage of e-wallet in Nainital city, so to record the response of respondent I selected market places, shopping malls, and the number of male respondent were 83 and females were 78 which include both users as well as those not using e-wallets. We have concluded our result on the basis of age, sex, occupation as well as from the detailed questionnaire we are able to concludes other findings related to the usage of e-wallets. Details of the research are as follow:

	Gender	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	MALE	83	51.6	51.6	51.6
	FEMALE	78	48.4	48.4	100.0

	Age	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	15-18	29	18.0	18.0	18.0
	18-35	101	62.7	62.7	80.7
	35-60	25	15.5	15.5	96.3
	60 AND ABOVE	6	3.7	3.7	100.0

	Occupation	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SALARIED	70	43.5	43.5	43.5
	AGRICUTURAL	40	24.8	24.8	68.3
	SELF OCCUPIED	23	14.3	14.3	82.6
	PROFESSION	28	17.4	17.4	100.0

2. To analyse if there is any association between use of e-wallet influenced by gender of respondents.

H₀₁ - There is no impact of Gender of respondents on e-wallet.

Ha₁- There is an impact of Gender of respondents on e-wallet.

	USAGE		Total
	yes	no	

GENDER	MALE	Count	68	15	83
		Expected Count	71.1	11.9	83.0
	FEMALE	Count	70	8	78
		Expected Count	66.9	11.1	78.0
Total		Count	138	23	161
		Expected Count	138.0	23.0	161.0

Table 5, Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.006 ^a	1	.157		
Continuity Correction ^b	1.419	1	.234		
Likelihood Ratio	2.038	1	.153		
Fisher's Exact Test				.181	.116
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.994	1	.158		
N of Valid Cases	161				

The Chi Square test is used to determine whether there is a correlation between a demographic trait, such as gender, and respondents' use of plastic and virtual money. This study examines if respondents' use of e-wallet differs depending on whether they are male or female.

3. To analyse if there is any association between uses of E-Wallet, Influenced by Age of Respondents.

H₀₂ - There is no impact of Age of respondents on the e-wallet.

Ha₂ - There is an impact of Age of respondents on the e-wallet.

Table 6, Cross Tabulation			USAGE		Total
			YES	NO	
AGE	15-18	Count	26	3	29
		Expected Count	24.9	4.1	29.0
	18-35	Count	93	8	101
		Expected Count	86.6	14.4	101.0
	35-60	Count	18	7	25
		Expected Count	21.4	3.6	25.0
	60 AND ABOVE	Count	1	5	6
		Expected Count	5.1	.9	6.0
Total		Count	138	23	161
		Expected Count	138.0	23.0	161.0

The Chi Square test is used to determine whether there is a correlation between a demographic attribute, such as age, and respondents' use of e-wallet. This study examines whether respondents' ages have any bearing on how they utilize e-wallets.

Table 7, Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	30.911 ^a	3	.000
Likelihood Ratio	21.793	3	.000

N of Valid Cases	161		
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3 cells (37.5%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .86.

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.438	.000
	Cramer's V	.438	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.401	.000
N of Valid Cases		161	

The strength of the relationship between the variables under consideration is determined using Cramer's V test. Since the result of the Cramer's V test is more than 0.25 (Cramer's $v = 0.438$), there is strong correlation between age and the use of e-wallet, indicating that age has a significant influence on both.

4. To analyse if there is any association between use of e-wallet influenced by occupation of respondents.

H₀₃. There is no impact of Profession of respondents on the e-wallet.

H_{a3} - There is an impact of Profession of respondents on the e-wallet.

			USAGE		Total	
			YES	NO		
OCCUPATION	SALARIED	Count	65	5	70	
		Expected Count	60.0	10.0	70.0	
	AGRICUTURAL	Count	25	15	40	
		Expected Count	34.3	5.7	40.0	
	SELF OCCUPIED	Count	23	0	23	
		Expected Count	19.7	3.3	23.0	
	PROFESSION	Count	25	3	28	
		Expected Count	24.0	4.0	28.0	
	Total		Count	138	23	161
			Expected Count	138.0	23.0	161.0

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	24.646 ^a	3	.000
Likelihood Ratio	24.040	3	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	.003	1	.955
N of Valid Cases	161		

2 cells (25.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.29.

The Chi Square test is used to determine whether there is a correlation between a demographic variable, such as the respondents' occupation, and whether they utilise e-wallet This aims to examine whether the respondents' profession has any bearing on how they use e-wallet.

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.391	.000
	Cramer's V	.391	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.364	.000
N of Valid Cases		161	

The Chi Square value is not Significant ($\chi^2 = 0.000$, $p > 0.05$), which shows that there is no significant relationship between profession and usage of e-wallets. It implies that the use of e-wallet is unaffected by one's occupation, i.e., one's occupation has no bearing on those who use e-wallets.

Findings

1. From the above data and its interpretation, it can be concluded that out of 161 respondents, 83 respondents were male and 78 respondents were female. This research was conducted to know the usage of e-wallets. Hence, Electronic Wallets as well as cards whether debit or credit both influenced by occupation of respondent self occupied and salaried respondents need transfer of money which he can easily opt by choosing e-wallets, Also it is affected by the age of respondent as young age is more aware of e-wallets and its benefits they are ever ready for dynamic environment. But aged group respondents hesitate while transaction through e-wallets
2. One of the main factors that contributes to the simplicity of using virtual currency is the ability to scan payment QR codes and transfer payments with a single click. While certain e-wallet shortcomings have been identified, including legal formalities (KYC verification), ignorance of such a payment method, and trust difficulties. Security concerns caused by the rise in cybercrime emerged as one important problem that was rather prevalent. People are unsure as to whether utilising E-Wallets will keep their money secure.
3. Additionally, it was shown that age has an impact on the use of electronic wallets, suggesting that younger generations are considerably more at ease utilising them than older generations. Reasons for the numerous rewards include cash back, discounts on various purchases, and accessible coupons for different eatables and recharges. Additionally, it demonstrates how much more adaptable and at ease the younger generation is with change.
4. The null hypothesis – that there is no meaningful relationship between the respondent's gender and their views on the future of mobile wallets – fails to be rejected.
5. People in Nainital city are aware about e-wallet. And people are also supporting the digital payment system, But Nainital is a hilly area which is 37.8% village area. Where the standard of living of the people is very low, In such a situation, it is not easy for people to fully accept e-wallets in a cashless economy.

Conclusion

Only younger age groups (15–18, 19–35 Years) in India are more conscious of utilising electronic wallets compared to using cash, however older age groups (36–60 Years) should be encouraged to utilise these E-Wallets. The fact that needs attention are,

1. Not everyone owns a smart phone is one of the key reasons why people aren't embracing electronic wallets.
2. People have problems with security and trust.
3. Legal prerequisites such as KYC

References

1. A Study on E-Wallet Adoption Among Customers and Businesses in Delhi MSc Research Project MSC Fintech Shrey Bhagat x18189075@student.ncirl.ie
2. <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/definition/e-wallets>

3. Ahuja, A., & Joshi, R. (2018). Customer Perception towards Mobile Wallet . IJRDO-Journal of Business Management, 4(1).
4. BADRUDDIN, A. (2015). Financial Market Infrastructures: A Study on Payment and Settlement System in Indian Banking Sector. International Journal of Engineering Technology, Management and Applied Sciences, 3(2).
5. Chakraborty, S., & Mitra, D. (2018). A Study on Consumers' Adoption Intention for Digital Wallets in India. International Journal on Customer Relations, 6(1).
6. Chawla, D., & Joshi, H. (2019). Consumer attitude and intention to adopt mobile wallet in India - An empirical study. International Journal of Bank Marketing, 37(7), 1590-1618.
7. Dubey, N. (2019, December 06). RBI to introduce new prepaid payment instrument for digital transactions up to Rs 10,000. The Economic Times.
8. Jain, M., & Sabharwal, P. (2019). A STUDY OF RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES AND USAGE OF E-WALLETS. Delhi Business Review, 20(2).
9. Jain, M., & Singla, D. R. (2017). Digital Wallet: A handy Solution in the wake of Demonetisation. Biz and Bytes, 8(1).
10. <https://etrace.in/census/subdistrict/nainital-nainital-uttarakhand-340/>

